

QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF REINFORCEMENT DISPERSION IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A fine and homogenous distribution of the reinforcements is required to achieve an optimum reinforcing effect. However, there has been few studies on reinforcement distribution evaluation in the produced MMCs and most of the proposed techniques are based on qualitative microscopic MMC images analysis. This paper proposed a quantitative analysis technique of reinforcement dispersion in metal matrix composites. In this study, an automated dispersion analysis technique is proposed to quantify reinforcement dispersion in metal matrix composites. The technique first learns the characteristics of reinforcements and understand which characteristics differentiate them from other objects including matrix and boundaries. Then, from the trained characteristics, only reinforcements are extracted from the original image. Finally, the distances between each extracted reinforcement, called nearest neighbor (NN) distance, are measured. The actual distribution of NN distance is compared with the expected distribution, and the quality of particle dispersion can be quantified from their difference. The performance of the proposed technique is validated with two B₄C/Al6061 composite specimens with (1) stir casting and (2) hot rolling, respectively. Changed reinforcement dispersion with different manufacturing process is observed and quantified with the proposed technique. The first specimen has scale and shape parameters 87.3% and 77.6% to the ideal distribution, while the other one has 63.2% and 71.2%.

1 INTRODUCTION

Physical properties of metal matrix composites (MMCs), including specific strength, thermal stability, and wear resistance, can be tailored by adding appropriate reinforcements. [1] A fine and homogenous distribution of the reinforcements is required to achieve an optimum reinforcing effect [2]. Various manufacturing processes are proposed to improve reinforcement distribution and corresponding parameters are adjusted during process optimization of final products.

However, there has been few studies on reinforcement distribution evaluation in the produced MMCs and most of the proposed techniques are based on qualitative microscopic MMC images analysis [3]. As they are relying on experts' decision making, the analysis results are unreliable and do not give a quantitative measure. Though there have been several quantitative measurement techniques proposed including quadrat method [4], these techniques still require users to adjust parameters and the dispersion measurement results are affected by the adjustment.

In this study, an automated dispersion analysis technique is proposed to quantify reinforcement dispersion in metal matrix composites. The proposed technique automatically analyzes the

reinforcement distribution and gives a quantitative dispersion index with minimized human interruption. It extracts the reinforcements only from the microscopic image using the learned reinforcement characteristic. Then their dispersion is quantified from the inter-particle distances.

By integrating image processing, statistical analysis, and computational intelligence, the reinforcement dispersion is evaluated as quantified measures with minimized human interruption. The performance of the proposed technique is validated with B₄C/Al6061 metal matrix composite samples manufactured by different process.

2 QUANTITATIVE DISPERSION ANALYSIS

The proposed technique includes following three steps: (1) reinforcement characteristic training; (2) reinforcement extraction; and (3) quantitative dispersion analysis. The program first learns the characteristics of reinforcements and understand which characteristics differentiate them from other objects including matrix and boundaries. Then, from the trained characteristics, only reinforcements are extracted from the original image. Finally, the distances between each extracted reinforcement, called nearest neighbor (NN) distance, are measured. The actual distribution of NN distance is compared with the expected distribution, and the quality of particle dispersion can be quantified from their difference. Figure 1 depicts the scheme of the proposed technique and represents the process of the aforementioned three steps.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the proposed technique

2.1 Reinforcement characteristic training

In this step, a user let the program, the proposed technique, understand the characteristics of a reinforcement image. First, the user select a small subsection from the full microscopic image. This subsection should include a single reinforcement and matrix only and should not contain any other objects e.g. cracks and impurities.

If we draw a line passing through the reinforcement, this line always meets two local minimum (dark) image value and one local maximum (bright) image value. The local minima are corresponding to the reinforcement-image boundary and the local maximum is corresponding to the reinforcement.

By drawing enough number of lines passing through the reinforcement and collecting the image values, distributions of boundary image values and reinforcement values are obtained. Then the program

performs a statistical analysis to the distributions and set the confidence interval of image values at the reinforcement, the matrix, and the reinforcement-matrix boundary.

2.2 Reinforcement extraction

The program now extracts reinforcements from the full microscopic image using the obtained image value confidence intervals from Step (1). If an image region is consisted as matrix image value – boundary image value – reinforcement image value – boundary image value – matrix image value, this region is considered as a reinforcement surrounded by boundary. Figure 2 presents an example of a reinforcement extraction from grayscale image values.

Defects and impurities, which have different image values from the matrix but do not have reinforcement characteristics, are effectively removed through this process. As their image values do not match with the reinforcement image value confidence interval and they are not surrounded by the boundary image values, they are not considered as a reinforcement.

Figure 2: Reinforcement extraction using image value confidence intervals

2.3 Dispersion analysis

Finally, the nearest neighbor (NN) distances between the extracted reinforcements are calculated from the processed image. The perfect distribution of reinforcements in metal matrix follows Weibull distribution, as gas molecules do in a free space [5]. The ideal distribution of NN distance $P(r)$ is given by

$$P(r) = \frac{3}{a} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^2 e^{-\left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^3}, \quad (1)$$

where r is the NN distance and $a = \sqrt[3]{3V/4\pi N}$ is Wigner-Seitz radius. Here we assume that there are N particles in volume V , where N is large enough. As we take care of particle dispersion in a 2D image not in a 3D space, Equation (1) becomes

$$P(r) = \frac{2}{a} \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^2 e^{-\left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^2}, \quad (1)$$

and this distribution follows the Weibull distribution $W(\lambda, k) = \frac{k}{\lambda} \left(\frac{r}{\lambda}\right)^{k-1} e^{-\left(\frac{r}{\lambda}\right)^k}$ where scale parameter $\lambda = a$ and shape parameter $k = 2$.

Therefore, by fitting the obtained NN distances to Weibull distribution, the actual reinforcement distribution and the ideal reinforcement distribution can be compared. The quality of the actual particle dispersion is quantified from the ratio between actual scale/shape parameters and the expected scale/shape parameters of the NN distance distribution.

3 EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATIONS

3.1 Experimental setup

To validate the performance of the proposed technique, a B₄C/Al6061 composite is used. This composite is first manufactured by stir casting and hot rolling is carried out as a post process. The stir casted composite is pre-heated to 600 °C and rolled by 10 meter per minute. Microscopic images of the final product are collected using an optical microscope. For the validations, two specimens with before and after rolling are prepared and their reinforcement distributions are compared.

3.2 Results and discussions

Figure 3: (a) Raw microscopic image, (b) reinforcement extraction results using the proposed technique, and (c) NN distance distribution of the stir casted specimen

Figure 3 presents (a) the obtained raw microscopic image and (b) the processed image of the first specimen without rolling using the proposed technique. Figure 3 (b) effectively extracts the reinforcements only, and defects and impurities are removed. By calculating the NN distances between each reinforcements, a red histogram in Figure 3 (c) is obtained and fitted as Weibull distribution. The fitted scale (28.3257) / shape parameters (1.5512) are less than those of the black ideal distribution in Figure 3 (c) (32.4416 / 2), 87.3% and 77.6%, respectively. This implies that the current reinforcement dispersion cannot be considered to be the best.

Figure 4 presents the results for the other specimen after hot rolling process. Still Figure 4 (b) effectively extracts the reinforcements only, and defects and impurities are removed. By calculating the NN distances between each reinforcements, a blue histogram in Figure 4 (c) is obtained and fitted as

Weibull distribution. The fitted scale (24.6050) / shape parameters (1.4246) are less than those of the black ideal distribution in Figure 4 (c) (38.9490 / 2), 63.2% and 71.2%, respectively. Therefore it is found that the given hot rolling process do not help to improve reinforcement dispersion. Please note that this results does not imply inappropriateness of hot rolling process for reinforcement dispersion. By adjusting parameters including rolling temperature and speed, it can improve the dispersion in metal matrix composites.

Figure 4: (a) Raw microscopic image, (b) reinforcement extraction results using the proposed technique, and (c) NN distance distribution of the hot rolled sample

4 CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a quantitative analysis technique of reinforcement dispersion in metal matrix composites. The proposed technique automatically analyzes the reinforcement distribution and gives a quantitative dispersion index with minimized human interruption. It extracts the reinforcements only from the microscopic image using the learned reinforcement characteristic. Then their dispersion is quantified from the inter-particle distances.

The performance of the proposed technique is validated with two B₄C/Al6061 composite specimens. The authors' group is currently relating the MMC manufacturing parameters and the dispersion index to optimize the MMC manufacturing process.

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